

Can Thymoquinone and Zinc (Active Constituents of *Nigella Sativa*) Be Used Against COVID-19?

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic emerged in China in December 2019. Caused by a pathogen called SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19 has infected millions of people worldwide. The SARS-CoV-2 causative agent of COVID-19 belongs to beta coronaviruses. Due to the fast spread and increasing mortality rate, cost-effective and internationally available COVID-19 vaccines with maximum therapeutic effects are under clinical trials. This review article will therefore demonstrate the potential impacts of Thymoquinone and Zinc (active constituents of *Nigella sativa*) as a therapeutic and preventive tool against SARS-CoV-2. Active components of *Nigella sativa* (common name: black seed) have shown historical significance as an effective herbal remedy that preserves balanced inflammatory response through chronic inflammation suppression as well as upgrading host immune response.

Thymoquinone (volatile oil) is the main component of *N. sativa*. It possesses anti-inflammatory, hepato-protective and anti-oxidant characteristics. Molecular docking studies proposed that thymoquinone suppresses SARS-CoV-2 by interfering with ACE2 receptors. HSPA5 (Heat Shock Protein A5) was considered to be a possible path for SARS-CoV-2 attachment and entry. Thymoquinone has a binding affinity with 6LU7 (protein of SARS-CoV-2), ACE2 and HSPA5. In this way, thymoquinone blocks the viral entry into the host cell.

Against any infectious agent like bacteria and viruses, zinc is systematically concerned with cell-mediated immunity. Coronaviruses belong to the Positive-stranded RNA (+RNA) viruses. Such

viruses require RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp) enzymes for their replication process. Zn^{2+} directly impairs nidovirus RNA synthesis. Another core enzyme for viral replication and assembly of functional viral proteins is SARS-CoV papain-like protease 2; the activity of this enzyme is also inhibited by Zn. For the treatment of COVID-19, zinc-chelating agents such as citrate and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) alone or in combination are expected. Persons suffering from low levels of Zn are more susceptible to viral infections.